

M. Bianchi, F. Valentini, G. Fredi, A. Dorigato, A. Pegoretti

University of Trento, Department of Industrial Engineering and INSTM Research Unit

INTRODUCTION

- **EPDM foams** are employed for **thermal insulation** of pipes and buildings. Their installation in confined spaces is often complicated → A **shape memory behavior would help** to overcome this limitation.
- **TES properties** would be desirable when EPDM foams are used to thermal insulate **systems suffering from thermal fluctuations**.

AIM OF THE WORK : Conferring both TES properties and a shape memory behavior to EPDM foams using paraffin

EXPERIMENTAL

EPDM compound

Paraffin RT70HC (P)
T_m : 70 °C

Physical blowing agent
Micropearl® F82 (MP)

25-30 μm

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Melt compounding
T = 70 °C
ω = 50 rpm

Compression Molding
T = 170 °C
t = 20 min

EPDM/paraffin foam

EPDM_MP_P20

PARAFFIN

MICRO CAPSULES

50 μm

PREPARED FORMULATIONS: EPDM_MP EPDM_MP_P20 EPDM_MP_P40 EPDM_MP_P60

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

SHAPE MEMORY TESTS

Strain Fixity $SF(\%) = \frac{90-\alpha}{90} \cdot 100$

Strain Recovery $SR(\%) = \frac{\beta}{90} \cdot 100$

FIXABILITY

RECOVERY CAPABILITY

Images of the Recovery Process

- ↑ in SF with ↑ wt% of paraffin
- Complete fixing in EPDM_MP_P60
- Paraffin content affects the recovery process
- ↑ wt% of paraffin ↓ SR at a given time
- Foams return to the permanent shape in a maximum time of 13 min

DSC ANALYSIS AND TES PROPERTIES

- T_{m1}, T_{m2}, T_c comparable to the ones of neat RT70HC
- ↑ ΔH_{m2} with ↑ wt% of paraffin
- EPDM foams exhibit **good thermal energy storage capabilities**

Sample	T _{m1} (°C)	T _c (°C)	T _{m2} (°C)	ΔH _{m2} (J/g)	PCM ^{eff} _{m2} (%)
RT70HC	68.4	66.9	69.4	276.1	100.0
EPDM_MP_P20	67.4	58.9	67.7	44.4	16.1
EPDM_MP_P40	69.9	59.6	69.4	96.1	34.8
EPDM_MP_P60	70.6	63.7	70.3	145.7	52.8

CYCLIC DSC ANALYSIS

- Cyclic DSC tests were performed to evaluate the retention of the TES effect over cyclic condition
- The thermograms at different cycles are overlapped
- The **thermal properties** of EPDM/paraffin foams **are stable up to 20 cycles**

CONCLUSIONS

- EPDM/paraffin foams show **good thermal energy storage capabilities**
- Paraffin strongly **improves the shape memory behavior** of EPDM foams

POSSIBILITY TO BE USED FOR THERMAL MANAGEMENT

GREAT POTENTIAL TO IMPROVE THE INSTALLATION IN CONFINED SPACES

REFERENCES

M. Bianchi, F. Valentini, G. Fredi, A. Dorigato, A. Pegoretti. *Thermo-Mechanical Behavior of Novel EPDM Foams Containing a Phase Change Material for Thermal Energy Storage Applications*. *Polymers* 2022, 14, 4058.